

ABSORPTION AND FLUORESCENCE SPECTRA OF FLAVONOLS

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Absorption and fluorescence spectra of a number of flavonols (with 4'-OCIL₁ or 4'-OCH₂φ substitution) and flavonol-acetates have been reported and discussed. The additional absorption band in flavonol and its derivatives is due to keto-enol tautomerism. 4'-OCH₂R (R = H, φ) group produces a bathochromic effect which is due to the increase in resonance by this substitution. Benzoyl group in 6-position modifies the spectrum radically, while conversion of 5-OH to 3-O.CO.CH₃ reverts the spectrum to that of flavone.

Fluorescence spectrum of flavonols has two bands in the visible. 4'-OCH₃ and 4'-OCH₂φ groups increase and benzoyl group greatly reduces the fluorescence efficiency. Acetylation of the hydroxyl at 3-position tends to revert the fluorescence spectrum to that of flavone, but there is a considerable decrease in efficiency.

Skarzynski (*Biochem. Z.*, 1939, **301**, 150) has shown that flavonol (3-hydroxy-flavone) spectrum has an additional absorption band in the long-wave region, compared to other flavone spectra. This has been attributed to the possibility of tautomerism.

Study of fluorescence spectra of flavones or flavonols has not been reported so far. Qualitative study of the exhibition of fluorescence of flavones (including 3-hydroxy derivative) in relation to structural factors has been done by Seshadri and his co-workers (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, **12A**, 375; 1951, **34A**, 319). Their work includes visual observation of the fluorescence, excited by daylight. Exciting radiation has not been considered in arriving at the conclusions.

The present work on absorption and fluorescence spectra of flavonols is discussed below. The data are shown graphically in Figs. 1-4.

Absorption

The flavonol spectra are a superposition of the spectra of two individual components present in different proportion, keto form being predominant. Flavonol shows another band in the 210 mμ region (not exactly located, as it was just beyond the range of the instrument under the experimental conditions) in addition to the three known bands at 240 (broad), 307 and 345 mμ. Due to the ionisation of the enol-tautomer, a regular change in absorption with p_H is observed. The absorption of the ionic form is higher in the region 400 mμ, while it is lower in the regions 340 and 300 mμ, as compared to that of the molecular form. The same is observed, though very prominently, with 7-hydroxycoumarins and chromones (work under publication). This p_H -dependence of absorption is shown in a similar manner by all other flavonols (not their acetates) studied here.

FIG. I

FIG. 2

FIG. 4

FIG. 3

Fluorescence

Flavonols differ from flavones in exhibiting an emission which has quite a different spectral distribution. The emission (visually green) has two bands, one comparatively weak in the blue and the other strong band in green. It is quite probable that the two bands are given rise to by the corresponding two long-wave absorption bands. This would mean that the weaker blue band is due to the absorption in the relatively weak 'enol-band', while the stronger green emission band is due to absorption in the "keto-band". However, the frequency interval between the two emission bands is, in general, more than that between the corresponding absorption bands of the flavonols studied here.

Flavonol shows a very weak and broad band in the blue ($\sim 440 \text{ m}\mu$), while a comparatively strong maximum at $535 \text{ m}\mu$. 4'-OMe substitution increases the emission, the relative $\int F d\nu$ being 1, 130 compared to 740 for flavonol, though there is also a corresponding increase in $\int \epsilon d\nu$ from 66.8 to 76.7. The blue band at $435 \text{ m}\mu$ for the former is comparatively much strong; relative F_{max} at this wave-length being 208 and 32 for 4'-methoxyflavonol and simple flavonol respectively.

Introduction of methyl group at 6- or 7- position of 4'-methoxyflavonol increases the total fluorescence and also the efficiency slightly. There is no change in the position of the fluorescence bands. With the replacement of 4'-OCH₃ by 4'-OCH₃CH₃ there is no significant change except a slight increase in efficiency. But when 6-Me- 3'-OMe or 7-3'-diOMe groups are introduced in 4'-benzyloxyflavonol, a large increase in efficiency (about 2 times) results. This increase is much less than that found in flavones (7-8 times) as a result of these substitutions. The blue band of the emission is shifted to $465 \text{ m}\mu$ (from $440 \text{ m}\mu$), while there is no significant shift in the maximum at $540 \text{ m}\mu$.

6-Benzoyl derivative of 4'-methoxyflavonol behaves similar to the corresponding flavone in having a large decrease in efficiency ($\int \epsilon d\nu$ and relative $\int F d\nu$ for 6-benzoyl-4'-methoxy and 4'-methoxy being 112.2, 130 and 76.7, 1, 130 respectively) and also a red-shift in the green maximum ($\Delta\lambda = 10 \text{ m}\mu$). The large decrease in efficiency may be due to hindrance of the normal electron drift towards pyrone oxygen at 4-position, by the introduction of an electrophilic benzoyl group.

With acetylation of the hydroxyl of the flavonols, their behaviour reverts to that of the corresponding flavones (*vide supra*). Now the emission is mainly blue. The fluorescence band has the same position as that of the corresponding flavone (λ^F_{max} , 6-Me, 4'-OCH₃-flavone = $425 \text{ m}\mu$; λ^F_{max} , 6-Me-4'-OCH₃-flavonol-acetate = $425 \text{ m}\mu$). However, a very slight flavonol character remains in as much as a comparatively very weak band at $530 \text{ m}\mu$ persists. Acetylation, besides, results in a large decrease in fluorescence efficiency: $\int \epsilon d\nu$ and relative $\int F d\nu$ for the flavone and flavonol-acetate, cited above, are 85.7, 1170 and 82.0, 425 respectively. Had the link —O— behaved as perfect insulator, then —O—CO—CH₃ group should not have hindered any normal electron drift towards the pyrone oxygen at 4-position, and the efficiency would have been similar to that of the corresponding flavone.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Absorption measurements have been done with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer and fluorescence spectra obtained with a spectrofluorimeter described by Jatkar and Mattoo (*J. Univ. Poona*, 1954, No. 6, 67).

Absorption spectra were measured in aqueous alcohol (87%) in neutral, $10^{-4}N$. HCl and $10^{-4}N$ -KOH solutions, while the fluorescence was studied of alcoholic (96%) solutions. Concentrations were throughout kept at $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$. The accuracy in the measurement of ϵ is within 1% and $\bar{\nu}_{max}$ are correct to $\pm 0.2\%$. For measuring the integrated absorption (limits 2, 100 Å and 5, 000 Å) and fluorescence, the areas under the respective spectral curves (on $\bar{\nu}$ scale) were measured planimetrically. In a qualitative comparison of fluorescence efficiencies of these compounds, the spectral distribution in the exciting radiation has not been taken into account.

The compounds used were pure as judged by their m.p.'s.

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